

Developing tools that assist with design support approaches to promote cropping system diversification

Problem

The design of diversified cropping systems for the agro-ecological transition requires operational tools, adapted to local pedo-climatic conditions, to support the decision-making of farmers or advisors (Le Gal et al. 2011, Duru et al. 2015).

Solution

A prototype of a dashboard has been developed that can help farmers to design and evaluate innovations. The dashboard, co-developed with Case Study 14 (dealing with the diversification of arable cropping systems) addresses concrete agronomic problems, for instance how to lower rapeseed susceptibility to pest damage. Farmers/advisors can either use directly this 'robust rapeseed dashboard', or could construct their own.

Benefits

The dashboard:

- Allows for the identification of solutions adapted to the local pedo-climatic context and expectations of the farmer
- Reinforces the farmer's learnings and decision-making autonomy
- Increases awareness of the importance of soil fertility and contributes towards the development of cropping practice diversification (e.g., intercropping)

Practical recommendations

Several steps are needed to (i) build your own dashboard (a construction guide is being written), (ii) use it to identify innovations to be tested, (iii) evaluate the tested innovations and identify areas for improvement:

- Define the major agronomic problem(s) specific to a farm, or common to a territory
- Define the desired outcomes for the farm(s)
- Identify key agronomic steps and objectives to be achieved, and the cause-effect relationships needed to reach the expected result, by bringing together the expertise of farmers and specialists
- Create the dashboard, listing the objectives, key stages and key practices (figure 2)
- Identify possible practices and provide guidance to each farmer to choose the ones that they want to implement

Applicability box

Theme

Learning, Barriers and enablers, Assessment, Multiple cropping, Intercropping, Rotation, Field

Agronomic conditions

All farming systems

Application time

Beginning of the cropping season to identify innovations to be tested. End of the cropping season to evaluate the success of the implemented innovations

Required time

To build the dashboard: at least one workshop (one day) and several round trips.

To carry out the observations to feed the dashboard: very variable depending on the case. Plan for at least 3 key dates with one day to make observations for about ten fields.

To the analysis and feedback: 1/2 day in group

Period of impact

One cropping season

Equipment

Only if specific observations are needed

Best in

All farming systems (dashboards have also been developed for various other themes)

Figure 1: Result of the implementation of the robust rapeseed dashboard for the assessment of a farmer's field (Sauzet/Terres Inovia). Red, yellow and green colours mean unsatisfactory, average satisfactory and satisfactory state, respectively.

Figure 2: Overall structure of the robust rapeseed dashboard co-designed with Case study14 (CS14) (Sauzet and Cadoux/Terres Inovia)

- Fill in the dashboard based on observations during the cropping season, according to the indicators selected (figure 1)
- Assess the results, identify bottlenecks and areas for improvement for the next cropping season.

Further information

Further readings

- Duru M et al. 2015. How to implement biodiversity-based agriculture to enhance ecosystem services: a review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*. 35(4):1259-81.
- Le Gal P-Y et al. 2011. How does research address the design of innovative agricultural production systems at the farm level? A review. *Agricultural Systems*. 104(9):714-28.
- Sauzet et Cadoux 2019. Réussir son implantation pour obtenir un colza robuste. Eds Terres Inovia. 37p.

Weblinks

- <https://www.terresinovia.fr/p/guide-technique-reussir-son-implantation-pour-obtenir-un-colza-robuste> (details of the robust rapeseed dashboard)
- <https://www.terresinovia.fr/web/institutionnel/-/outillage> (toolkit for farmer support (forthcoming))

About this practice abstract and DiverIMPACTS

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DiverIMPACTS: The project is running from June 2017 to May 2022. The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS - Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple Cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains towards Sustainability - is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains.

Project website: www.diverimpacts.net

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